

ENHANCING LEADERSHIP: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PARTICIPATIVE APPROACH IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the benefits and challenges of implementing a participative approach in educational institutions, focusing on its impact on communication, teamwork, accountability, and decision-making among the stakeholders such as teachers, students, parents, and school administrators. A systematic review approach was employed in the conduct of the study, analyzing data and information collected through a comprehensive literature review and examining the frequency of research articles related to participative approach in educational institutions. The study revealed that the participative approach enhances leadership qualities and promotes a sense of belonging and collective responsibility among the stakeholders. However, challenges such as lack of preparedness, inadequate training, and time constraints were identified as barriers to its successful implementation. Participative approach facilitates better decision-making and improves school performance by nurturing collaboration and trust among stakeholders. The study concluded that while the participative approach offers significant benefits, its effectiveness depends on overcoming initial barriers and providing support through training, professional development, and structured frameworks. Involving all stakeholders in decision-making and further collaborative efforts are essential strategies to enhance academic success and institutional effectiveness.

Keywords. *Participative approach, influence, effectiveness, leadership style*

INTRODUCTION

Participative approach, also known as democratic leadership, aims to actively encourage the engagement among members of the institution and to encourage participation in the collective decision-making of the group. (Bass, 1990). In educational institutions, this type of leadership approach intends to promote inclusivity by means valuing the inputs of teachers, staff, students, and parents in shaping institutional policies and practices. In addition, research indicates that the implementation of this leadership approach improves student success, teacher satisfaction, and institutional performance (Yukl & Gardner, 2013). Nevertheless, there are challenges to its implementation as well, such as decision-making delays, disputes arising from divergent opinions, and an increase in duties that could make educators feel more stressed (Tahir, Lee, Musah, Jaffri, Said, & Yasin, 2016). Despite the potential benefits, hierarchical systems, time constraints, and resistance to change sometimes limit the use of participatory approaches in educational institutions (Avolio & Gardner, 2005). The necessity of reaching a consensus can occasionally result in inefficiencies, and teachers may find it challenging to strike a balance between their teaching obligations and their participatory responsibilities. These difficulties cast doubt on the possible long-term effects of participative approach on institutional efficiency as well as its actual implementation. This study aims to conduct a thorough systematic review of the existing research on the effectiveness of participatory leadership in educational settings. Consequently, this study intends to conduct a systematic review that will examine the benefits and challenges of participative approach on decision-making procedures, stakeholders' involvement, and overall school leadership effectiveness by combining empirical research and theoretical viewpoints.

Research Questions:

1. What are the benefits and challenges of implementing a participative approach in educational institutions?
2. How does participative approach in educational leadership influence decision-making and institutional effectiveness?
3. What evidence-based strategies enhance the effectiveness of participative leadership in fostering collaboration and academic success?

METHODOLOGY

According to Siddaway et.al (2019) **systematic review approach** is commonly used in comprehensive search and locating of both published and unpublished articles or literature. This is used to draw a more comprehensive theoretical analysis on how things or practices work in the field. Systematic review approach also tries to make an analysis specifically on collecting and analyzing evidence available that can be useful in answering established research questions (Thacker, 2024).

The initial step to achieve the objectives of the study is to select a reputable database that holds and carries articles and literature about the keywords identified by the researchers of the study namely: participative approach, influence, effectiveness, leadership style. The study will be using the following database to gather necessary data for the systematic literature review: Academic.edu, Education Resource Information Center (ERIC), Google Scholar, EBSCO Education Source, JSTOR Education Section, Journal of Educational Analytics (JEDA), and ResearchGate. These are the identified eligible research-database driven that can sufficiently address the issue or problem stated above.

Nikolopoulou (2023) inclusion and exclusion criteria are set characteristics that will be used in determining the relevancy of the set criteria. With the use of the following database stated above and keywords, the study will analyze, collate, and organize an initial forty (40) pieces of literature.

Table 1. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Presence of at least one (1) discussion on participative leadership in education institutions.	Absence of discussion on participative leadership in educational settings.
Primary research published in peer-reviewed journals, dissertations, or conference proceedings.	Books reviews, editorial, opinion-based sites, and non-scholarly databases/sources.
Full paper must be accessible in the database.	Papers that only contain abstract and title without full access to it.
Research focusing on participative leadership in educational institutions.	Studies focusing on corporate or business leadership rather than educational institutions.
Research articles that are written in English (for accessibility and consistency in analysis)	Research articles written in other languages. (Unless a reliable English translation is provided)
Published articles from the year 2015-2025.	Research articles or papers that have yet to be published from 2015-2025.

RESULTS

Table II shows the research articles included in the systematic literature review along with the authors, research titles, and publication date.

Table 2. Research Articles included in the systematic review of literature

Research No.	Author/s	Research Title	Year of Publication
1	Sagnak, M.	Participative Leadership and Change-Oriented Organizational Citizenship: The Mediating Effect of Intrinsic Motivation	2016
2	Daloisio, T.	Participative Leadership in Education: Fostering Collaboration and Shared Success	2024
3	Owusu-Agyeman, Y.	Transformational Leadership and Innovation in Higher Education: A Participative Process Approach	2019
4	Buthelezi, A. B., & Ajani, O.	Transforming school management system using participative management approach in South Africa	2023
5	Manouchehri, B., & Burns, E. A.	A "Participatory School" in Iran: A Bottom-Up Learning Approach in a Top-Down Education System	2021
6	Nassir, M., & Benoliel., P.	The Differences in the Implications of Participative Decision-making and Paternalistic Leadership for Teachers' Perceived Stress in the Education System of the Israeli Arab Minority	2023
7	Abu Nasser, F. M.	The Application Degree of Participative School Leaderships at Al-Ihsa Governorate and Its Correlation with Teachers' Professional Development	2019
8	Salonen-Hakomäki, S. M., & Soini, T.	Citizenship Education: The Feasibility of a Participative Approach	2023
9	Al-Fayez, T. M.	The Role of Participatory Leadership in Developing Creativity and Increasing Teachers' Motivation toward Teaching in Saudi Schools	2024
10	Harianto, J. E.	The Role of Participatory Management in Improving Teacher Performance and Student Achievement	2024

11	Salonen-Hakomäki, S.-M., Soini, T., Pietarinen, J., & Pyhältö, K.	Leading Complex Educational Change Via National Participative Reforms? A Case of Finnish Core Curriculum Reform Leadership	2024
12	Suherni, E. S., Wahyudin, A., & Gunawan, A.	Analysis of Adaptive and Participatory Leadership Models Study of Educational Institutional Leadership Models	2023
13	Mataboge, C., & Khololo, S.	Examining Participative Management's Impact on Curriculum Decisions in Secondary Schools through Collaboration.	2024
14	Paulus, P., Zakso, A., & Rustiyarso, R.	Participatory Leadership of the School Principal in Developing the Quality of Education Services at State Senior High School	2024
15	Burhanuddin, B., Aspland, T., Darmawan, I. G. N., & Ben, F.	Leaders and Employees' Perspectives on Participative Management as an Empowerment Strategy to Improve University Employee Performance In Indonesia.	2023
16	Trent, S.	Participative Leadership: A Leadership Structure Within a School District. World Congress on Engineering.	2022
17	Amos, O., Siamoo, P., & Ogoti, E.	Influence of Collective Decision Making in Participative Leadership Style on Improving the Quality of Education in Public Secondary Schools in Arusha Region, Tanzania	2022
18	Arina, Y. ., Revita, Y., Gistituati, N. ., & Rusdinal, R.	The Influence of Principal's Participative Leadership Style and Work Climate on Public Middle School Teacher Performance	2023
19	Jaelani, A. K., Agung, A. A. G., Yudana, M., & Dantes, K. R.	The Influence of Participative Leadership, Organizational Climate, Organizational Commitment to Work Productivity of Vocational High School Teachers in Mataram City	2023

20	Ramos, R. C., & Bauyot, M. M.	Exploring the Impact of School Leadership on Professional Development in Panabo City Division, Philippines: A Mixed-Method Explanatory Research Study.	2024
21	Komariah, A., Kurniady, D. A., Abdullah, Z., & Sunaengsih, C.	Elementary School Principal Participative Leadership: Coordination in Character Education Implementation	2022
22	Imam Junaris.	The Influence of Participatory Leadership and Teacher Competence on Performance with Organizational Commitment	2023
23	Kosgei, A. C., & Edabu, P.	Head Teachers' Participative Leadership Style and Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Public Primary School in Baringo Sub-County, Kenya	2023
24	Torres, J. L., Abugan, M. D. Q., Ouano, A. A., Japinan, S. M. E., Peranco, R. E., & Ampil, F. D.	Leadership Styles and Their Impact on Educational Outcomes in the Philippines	2024
25	Akpoviroro, K. S., Kadiri, B., & Owotutu, S. O.	Effect of Participative Leadership Style on Employees Productivity	2018
26	Villafane, R.	Participative Leadership Style of School Heads: Implications for an Effective Academic Mentorship Program	2025
27	Suci Nabilah Balqis, Usman, N., & Ismail	Partnership in Participative Leadership and Organizational Communications: Factors Shaping Junior High School Teacher Performance.	2025
28	Almutairi, N. Z.	Participative Leadership as an	2024

		Approach to Achieving Local Excellence in Secondary Schools at Hail City	
29	Yudela Arina, Yuni Revita, Nurhizrah Gistituati, & Rusdinal Rusdinal.	The Influence of Principal's Participative Leadership Style and Work Climate on Public Middle School Teacher Performance	2023
30	Joyami, E. N., & Salmani, D	Role of participative leadership in the improvement of academic performance of students in the University of Tehran, Iran	2019
31	Mwania Johnson Kavita, Jeremiah Mutuku Kalai, & Ursulla Achieng Okoth	Influence of Principals' Participative Leadership Style on Tutors' Support for Implementation of Performance Appraisal in Public Primary Teachers Training Colleges in Kenya	2024
32	Sirisookslip, S., Ariratana, W., & Ngang, T. K.	The Impact of Leadership Styles of School Administrators on Affecting Teacher Effectiveness	2015
33	Morimoto, J. C., & Baguio, J. B.	Participative Leadership Practices and Professional Development of Language Teachers in Public Secondary Schools	2025
34	Abd, I. M., Zuhairi, M. M. K., & Kamil, G. H.	The Mediating Role of the Participatory Leadership Style on the Effect of Job Stress on Job Performance	2024
35	Hamal, R.	Participative Leadership Theory and its implication in Educational Administration and Management	2024
36	Almutairi, N.	Participative Leadership as an Approach to Achieving Local Excellence in Secondary Schools at Hail City	2024

37	Wang, Q., Hou, H., & Li, Z.	Participative Leadership: A Literature Review and Prospects for Future Research	2022
38	Khassawneh, O., & Elrehail, H.	The Effect of Participative Leadership Style on Employees' Performance: The Contingent Role of Institutional Theory	2022
39	Sağnak, M	Participative Leadership and Change-Oriented Organizational Citizenship: The Mediating Effect of Intrinsic Motivation	2016
40	Chan, S. C. H.	Participative leadership and job satisfaction: The mediating role of work engagement and the moderating role of fun experienced at work	2019

1. Benefits and Challenges of implementing a participative approach.

Benefits and challenges of implementing a participative approach in educational settings or things to consider in implementing this kind approach. Based on the literature gathered and identified below are the common benefits and challenges of implementing a participative approach in educational institutions.

Table 3. Benefits and Challenges of Implementing a Participative Approach in Educational Settings.

Benefits in Implementing a Participative Approach in Educational Settings	Research Article
Encourages Inclusive Decision-Making	
1. Shared Governance	1,2,3,4,5,7,11,19,21,24,28,35,36,37,39
2. Stakeholders Collaboration	1,2,3,4,5,7,9,10,13,15,20,25,27,29,35,36,37
Improves Learning Outcomes	
1. Active Learning	2,3,4,5
2. Personalized Learning	3,4,5,33

Develop Leadership Skills	
1. Critical Thinking	2,3,4,8,9
2. Decision-Making Activity	1,2,3,4,7,14,15,17,26,35,36,39
Foster Collaboration and Teamwork	
1. Cooperative Learning Strategies	3,4,9,10,33,39
2. Peer Support and Shared Responsibility	2,3,4,7,12,13,20,28,35,36,37,40
Strengthens Teacher-Administrator Relationships	
1. Open Communication and Transparency	2,3,4,7,21,36,27
2. Mutual Trust and Professional Support	2,3,4, 27,40
Challenges in Implementing a Participative Approach in Educational Unequal Participation	
1. Dominance of some teachers in the discussion.	6,13,23,34
2. Need for Strategies to Engage the Teachers	2,3,4,23
Assessment Difficulties	
1. Measuring diverse or individual responses.	2,3,4,38
2. Subjectivity	8,13,23,38
Balancing Authority and Autonomy	
1. Balance between guidance and independence.	1,3,4,11,12,32,37
2. Risk of Deviation	3,4,38
Time-Consuming	
1. Extensive Planning and Preparation	1,3,4
2. Lengthy Decision-Making	2,4
Resistance to Change	
1. Difficulty in adjusting to a new method or style.	2,3,4,11,38
2. Conflict with antiquated or traditional leadership style.	1,2,3,4

2. Influence of Participative Approach in Decision Making and Institutional Effectiveness.

The table illustrates the influence of participative leadership on decision-making processes and institutional effectiveness within educational settings.

Table 4. Influence of Participative Approach in Decision Making and Institutional Effectiveness

Influence of Participative Approach in Decision Making	Research Article
1. Inclusive Governance (involving all stakeholders)	1,2,3,4,5,11,13,35,36
2. Collaborative Problem-Solving	1,2,3,4,9,10,13,19,21,22,26,37
3. Transparency and Trust in Leadership	1,2,3,4
4. Empowerment and Accountability	1,2,3,4,37
Influence of Participative Approach in Institutional Effectiveness	
1. Improved Organizational Culture and Teamwork	1,2,3,4,22,25,26,29,32,36,37,40
2. Higher Engagement and Motivation to the Stakeholders	1,2,3,4,6,22,25,26,29,32,39,40
3. Efficient Policy Implementation	1,2,3,4,21,28,36
4. Sustainable institutional growth and adaptability.	1,2,3,4,25

3. Evidence-Based Strategies to Enhance Participative Leadership/Approach in Fostering Stakeholders' Collaboration and Academic Success

This table outlines research-supported strategies that aimed at strengthening participative leadership practices within educational institutions.

Table 5. Evidence-Based Strategies to Enhance Participative Leadership/Approach in Fostering Stakeholders' Collaboration and Academic Success

Encouraging Shared Decision-Making	Research Article
1. Establishing stakeholder-inclusive policy council.	1,2,3,4,5,12,13,36
2. Implementing Structured	1,3,4,22,27,30,36,37

Participative Leadership Framework	
3. Organizing periodic consultation, meeting, or forums.	1,2,3,4,9
Strengthening Teacher-Administrator Collaboration	
1. Co-developing curriculum and instructional materials.	1,3,4,13,33
2. Conducting Professional Learning Community (PLC) or Learning Action Cell (LAC)	2,3,4,10,20
3. Creating Feedbacks between teacher and administrator.	3,4
Enhancing Student Engagement in Leadership	
1. Integrating leadership training into student, teachers, and parents, develop programs	3,4,6,9,20,26,28
2. Encouraging students, teachers, and parents participation in institutional planning.	1,2,4,5,9,12,13,18,22,37
Strengthening Parent and Community Involvement	
1. Developing structured parent-school partnership.	1,2,4
2. Organizing interactive community-based learning projects.	1,3,4,9,31
Measuring and Sustaining Participative Leadership Impact	
1. Conducting Periodic Evaluation of participative strategies.	1,2,4
2. Recognizing and rewarding collaborative efforts.	1,2,3,4
3. Institutionalizing participative leadership as a core of educational value.	1,2,3,4,18

DISCUSSION

1. Benefits and Challenges of Implementing a Participative Approach.

The study revealed the benefits and challenges of implementing a participative approach as shown in Table 3 reveals that the participative approach improves leadership qualities such as communication, teamwork, accountability, and decision-making. Different stakeholders, including teachers, students, parents, and school administrators, benefit from collective participation in activities that build openness, cooperation, and respect for each other. Collective participation builds self-confidence, encourages accountability, and makes all stakeholders feel a sense of belonging to school activities. When different members of the education organization engage in planning and decision-making, it results in a greater sense of belonging and cooperation as per the frequency of research articles per item or variable. However, some challenges accompany this process. Some of the learning environments face the phenomenon of a lack of preparedness among the teaching personnel or administrative staff if they are used to working with a traditional leadership model. Others would fail to allocate adequate time between active participatory involvement and study. The lack of adequate training and assistance offered to instructors in adopting participative styles also affects the effectiveness of the approach. Such concerns show that although there are many benefits linked with the participative approach, caution and provision of support will be necessary before the approach is applied successfully to many school environments. The study of Villafane (2024) significantly highlights how participative leadership among school heads in the Schools Division of Bulacan positively influences collaboration, communication, and shared accountability. It supports the idea that involving stakeholders—teachers, parents, and community members—in decision-making builds a sense of ownership and trust within the school which is being emphasized in the frequency of literature in this table. The researcher of this study also identified common challenges, such as resistance to change, time limitations, and weak stakeholder engagement, which mirror earlier discussions on the need for adequate training and structured support when shifting from traditional leadership models. Therefore, while participative approach appears broadly effective, its implementation must consider local norms, institutional culture, and resource availability to ensure contextual fit especially in educational institutions.

Influence of Participative Approach in Decision-Making and Institutional Effectiveness.

Table 4 revealed that the participative approach makes better decisions by involving a large number of individuals in the decision-making process. The participative approach also provides opportunities for teachers, parents, students, and school administrators to make their contributions and ideas. This results in better decisions as they are based on the shared experience and expertise of the stakeholders. Participative leadership promotes collaboration, trust, and cooperation,

which help to establish better school relationships among the stakeholders in the institution. This approach also assists schools to perform more effectively by developing a sense of collective responsibility among their stakeholders. When all the stakeholders involved are interested in making decisions or solving issues, they are more engaged in the outcome. It assists educational institutions to handle problems and perform tasks more effectively and efficiently. The result of this literature review is significantly connected with the study conducted by Morimoto and Baguio (2025) in which they emphasized participative approach practices among public secondary school teachers. The study showed that participative leadership was frequently practiced and significantly associated with higher levels of professional growth among teachers which is connected with the result of this study.

2. Evidence-Based Strategies to Enhance Participative Leadership/Approach in Fostering Stakeholders' Collaboration and Academic Success

Table 5 indicated various strategies that make participative approach more effective in education institutions. One of the common strategies is including students, parents, and teachers in planning group activities and school events. Assigning specific roles to students, parents, and teachers allowing them to assist with group assignments facilitates teamwork and responsibility. Teachers are also provided with clear feedback systems and open communication, which facilitate improvement in relationships, active involvement, and learning. Another key tactic is providing assistance and training for teachers and administrators so they are able to use participative approach correctly. If proper guidance is not provided, it might not be easy to run a school or classroom in which numerous voices are heard. However, using methods such as feedback, collaborative working, and leadership development, schools can have a culture of cooperation in which all work collaboratively. Such strategies result in increased cooperation and can improve academic performance as well as leadership. In the study conducted by the Norp (2019), she emphasized that based on the conduct of her study, it was revealed that when stakeholders are involved in the decision-making process it has led to significant improvement to the students' learning outcomes.

Conclusions

The study explored the benefits and challenges, and strategic approaches to participative leadership. It revealed that this kind of approach enhances communication, teamwork, accountability, and decision-making among stakeholders, promoting a sense of shared responsibility and belonging within the school community. However, challenges such as resistance to change, inadequate training, and time constraints hinder its effective implementation among the other educational institutions. To address these challenges, the study highlighted the importance of providing proper guidance, professional development, and structured frameworks that will facilitate participative practices among the stakeholders. Furthermore, involving all stakeholders in the decision-

making and nurturing collaborative efforts were identified as key strategies that will enhance academic success and institutional effectiveness. In conclusion, while participative approach offers various significant potential for educational improvement, its success relies on overcoming initial barriers and ensuring continued support and training for all involved.

Compliance with the Ethical Standards

The researchers of this study affirm that there are no conflicts of interest, biases and the systematic review is solely focused on analyzing existing studies related to participative approach in educational institutions.

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